

C O R T E X ²

D6.4 – Third-party achievements and impacts version 1

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D6.4 Third part achievements and impact version 1

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Abstract

The deliverable presents a detailed overview of CORTEX² Open Call 1 Programme focusing on the 20 selected projects and presenting their work progress. The core part includes projects portfolios divided into 10 co-developers' projects and 10 use-cases, demonstrating their expected results, impact and achievements up to date.

The document outlines the management structure on the following activities: 1) Monitoring work of the funded projects; 2) Mentoring Third Parties in a form of key technical contact point bridge; 3) Evaluation of the results.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AWU	Annual Work Unit
AR	Augmented Reality
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamic
CORTEX ²	COoperative Real-Time experiences with EXTended reality
EC	European Commission
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report
FSTP	Funding for the Third Parties
GA	Grant Agreement
HCI	Human Computer Interaction
HMD	Head Mounted Display
IoT	Internet of things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MR	Mixed Reality
MS	Member States
NLP	Natural language processing
OC	Open Call
OCT	Overseas Countries and Territories
POC	Proof of Concept
R&D	Research and Development
RTO	Research and Technology Organizations
SDK	Software Development Kit
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
STO	Standard Operating Procedure
T	Track
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

The CORTEX² project

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **extended reality (XR) experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation**, and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at

1. recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX²
2. engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths
3. assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

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1. Introduction

The project consortium with F6S as a leading partner organised and executed two Open Calls (OC) **investing nearly €4.000.000** to explore, advance and validate the technical features offered by CORTEX² through targeting 3rd parties (technology developers, providers, integrators and adopters) with knowledge and expertise in XR remote collaboration.

Both Open Calls attracted in total 237 applications, from which the top 30 were selected (OC1 – 20; OC2 – 10). Detailed process of OC1 and OC2 management is described in submitted deliverables D6.3 and D6.6. There is one more deliverable¹ scheduled for February 2025 regarding the OC execution.

This deliverable focuses on presenting the first achievements from beneficiaries of OC1, mainly:

- 10 projects funded to co-develop CORTEX² features during 9-month work programme
- 10 projects funded as use-cases to deploy and validate CORTEX² technology during 12-month work programme

OC2 selected projects just kicked off (November 2024), hence their first achievements will be known only by January 2025, and they will be reported in the final deliverable².

The document demonstrates the third-party projects portfolios (20 from OC1), a form of engagement in the CORTEX² project including monitoring and mentoring activities of the progress, a review system to evaluate the third-party performance through deliverables and KPIs check. Finally, it reveals the expected impact from the funded projects.

1.1. Overview of the Beneficiaries

CORTEX² project ran two OCs across 2023 and 2024. The winning projects from both calls are represented by 41 Beneficiaries from 13 countries and 7 types of organizations: SMEs, Startups, Research Organizations, Universities, Governmental Organizations, Foundations and Non-governmental organizations (Figure 1).

¹ D6.7 Open Call Management from preparation to selection version 3. Results of the T6.4 and T6.5: Open Call objectives, documents and FSTP implemented procedures up to the selection and engagement of the third-parties.

² D6.8: Third-party achievements & impacts version 2. Third-party projects portfolio, their engagement in the project activities, achievements, deliverables and results assessment. Measurements of the CORTEX² impacts on third-party projects and vice-versa.

DIVERSITY AMONG SELECTED 3rd PARTIES

Figure 1 Overview of the selected 3rd parties (OC1 and OC2)

1.1.1. OC1 Track 1 for co-developers

There are 10 selected projects represented by 10 Beneficiaries: SMEs (6) and Startups (4) from 8 countries: France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, Ukraine. The selected teams cover proposals to develop technological solutions to the seven Topics (T) listed below.

- ✓ **T1** User representation and user avatar customisation
- ✓ **T2** Real-time object virtualiser
- ✓ **T3** Collaborative hand object manipulation
- ✓ **T4** IoT adaptability of the CORTEX² framework
- ✓ **T5** Dynamic library of personalised gestures
- ✓ **T6** 3D objects library
- ✓ **T11** Open - own project idea

1.1.2. OC1 Track 2 for use-cases

There are 10 selected projects represented by 21 Beneficiaries: SMEs (5) and Startups (1) from 8 countries: France, Greece, Ireland, North Macedonia, Poland, Portugal, Spain, The

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Netherlands. The selected teams applied as technology adopters and technology provider/developer/integrator to cover pilots' proposals for the seven Domains (D) listed below:

- ✓ **D1** Education
- ✓ **D2** Business
- ✓ **D3** Industry
- ✓ **D4** Healthcare
- ✓ **D5** Emergency and crisis
- ✓ **D6** Entertainment and culture
- ✓ **D7** Smart cities
- ✓ **D8** Accessibility and Social inclusion
- ✓ **D9** Open Domain

Given the timeline of this deliverable, the content will reflect only Open Call 1 from both tracks. A list of portfolios and results from OC2 will be introduced in D6.8.

2. Achievements

The CORTEX² Open Call programme manages progress from the from 3rd parties following a roadmap (Figure 2) with three check points aligned with the requirements for co-developers and use-cases. By applying to the OC1, each Beneficiary agreed to comply with the list of such requirements included in the Guidelines for Applicants. The sections Monitoring, Mentoring, and Evaluation details the process of execution.

In section Third Party Project Portfolios, each funded project description contains a summary of the key achievements, including the name of submitted deliverable(s) and achieved KPIs³, if applicable. In addition, summary of the achievements per funded project will be published on the project website: <https://cortex2.eu/open-call-1-winners/>

In this part, we present a structure with expected results from each of the Sprints (for co-developers) and Phases (for use-cases), and the general status of achievements by November 2024.

Figure 2 Open Call 1 roadmap of progress execution

2.1. 9-month programme for co-developers

Sprints programme OC1 Track 1		
Sprint Name	Objective	Expected results

³ KPIs are not assigned per each Sprint/Phase, but along the project duration.

Sprints programme OC1 Track 1		
Development - 3 months	Fine tune planning & technology usage of CORTEX2	Detailed project plan. Technologies used, Report on technical developments. Detailed list of KPIs and milestones with metrics
Integration - 3 months	Implementation & integration	Configuration of units and software. Reporting of the operation initiation and technology deployment by the end-user. Collection of relevant data. Project performance (in terms of quantitative KPIs identified in the previous phase). Proof that the CORTEX2 tech offering has been used and integrated for the project purposes. Provide a Demo (including a video to be published on the CORTEX2 YouTube channel)
Validation - 3 months	Validate the co-development performed and foster the exploitation of the project results	A demonstrator and a report on the developed feature. For exploitation: a business plan for the exploitation of the result. Presentation of the final module with a documentation. Validation of the source code of the final product, if applicable. Upload the source code on a repository on git, if applicable.

Status of the achievements from Sprint 1 (Jul - Oct 2024):

All funded projects from OC1 Track 1 **accomplished the expectations from the first 3 months** of the programme (Sprint 1). Details regarding evaluation are included in section 4.3.

2.2. 12-month programme for use-cases

Phases programme OC1 Track 2		
Phase Name	Objective	Expected results
Requirements - 3 months	Set the implementation plan, incl. key requirements and roadmap for the use-case	Description of how the project will be carried out (including plan for POC) Description of the technologies to use Report on technical developments Detailed list of deliverables, KPIs and milestones with metrics

Phases programme OC1 Track 2		
		User stories if applicable
Development & Deployment - 5 months	Perform the use-case development and deployment, based on the implementation plan	Development and showcase of an MVP Provision of a Technical and Performance Report, incl. the collection of relevant data Provision of proof of achieved KPIs as per the requirements and implementation plan
Validation - 4 months	Validate the use case and foster the exploitation of the project results	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment (TRL7) Deliverables and KPIs required as per Track 2 Proposal for an exploitation plan Video demonstrating the use-case Report of a user-study to assess the use case, with a minimum of 10 users

Status of the achievements from Phase 1 (Jul - Oct 2024):

All funded projects from OC1 Track 2 **accomplished the expectations from the first 3 months** of the programme (Phase 1 – Requirements). Details regarding evaluation are included in section **4.3**.

3. Third party project portfolios

3.1. OC1 co-developers

3.1.1. ARY - The AR Media

	https://ary.eu/index.php/en/
<p>ARY SAS is a young innovative company created in 2022 by Eric and Marie-Pierre Heurtier, long-time entrepreneurs in the field of RFID in an international context. Today, they put their experience to the benefit of ARY SAS. ARY is supported and hosted in France by the Ecole Polytechnique (X) and labelled « France 2030 »</p> <p>ARY is an AR technology, which offers the capability to anchor virtual elements (3D objects...) into indoor environment and make them available to anyone using a smartphone.</p>	<p>France</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>ARY</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>ARY the AR Media</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>By adopting the ARY technological proposal, CORTEX users will be able, with current smartphone and tablet (UWB native or not), to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anchor virtual objects in their library with a precision of 10cm in the real world. • Share identical AR scenes. • Remotely manage the positioning of virtual objects.
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The precision provided by UWB will make it possible to optimize the various use cases defined in the CORTEX² Pilots. • Demonstrate the relevance of AR as a communication media.
<p>First achievements</p>	<p>Interface ARY IoT beacons with CORTEX Server.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified design of the beacons with specified components • UWB beacons ready: 5 concurrent users per 3 beacons
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. 3x UWB beacons ready to be connected to uiTOP platform</p>

3.1.2. CDPLG - Co-development of a Dynamic library of personalized gestures

	https://sensoramalab.com/	
<p>Sensorama Lab is a VR/AR development company that provides B2B and B2G applications in Unity and Unreal Engine with multiplayer functionality, hand tracking, voice commands, AI integration, and precise gestures with sign-to-action capabilities.</p> <p>In 2023, Sensorama Lab was rated in the top 5 AR/VR companies in the world according to Clutch.</p>		<p>Ukraine</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>CDPLG</p>	
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Co-development of a Dynamic library of personalized gestures</p>	
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>To improve user experience and promote wider application of VR/AR in the industry through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing gesture recognition module capable of interpreting specific hand or body gestures, allowing users to trigger distinct actions. • The gesture library dynamically extendable, supporting personalized application-specific gestures. 	
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enriched educational and training experiences • Intuitive AR/VR UX for natural user engagement • Dynamic gesture library tailored to wide range of users • Gesture library growth for application across sectors. • Economic uplift in the AR/VR domain, opening new markets and opportunities. 	
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video showcasing demo • Technical specification 	
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Module analysis and integration plan.</p>	

3.1.3. EXTERNALISE - Enabling support for externalizing models in XR collaboration

	https://moverse.ai/	
<p>Moverse is a deep-tech startup committed to accelerating 3D character animation workflows.</p> <p>At Moverse, we are on a mission to make 3D animation more accessible, reducing the resources needed. We deliver an end-to-end 3D animation workflow, from real-time Motion Capture to ready-to-be-used generative 3D animation tools and services. Our goal is to revolutionize 3D character animation by delivering next-generation, optimized and power-efficient software tools and services.</p>		<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>EXTERNALISE</p>	
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Enabling support for externalizing models in XR collaboration</p>	
<p>Expected Result</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XR-based communication closer to natural exchanges. Focus on digital “externalising modes” to mirror natural communication interactions. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deploy a system using markerless capture technology to perceive users at room scale ○ Integrate real-time multi-user markerless capture system into an EU telecollaboration platform ○ Validate the system in collaboration with CORTEX through a co-designed and comprehensive validation plan. 	
<p>Impact</p>	<p>EXTERNALISE will contribute to the goal for scalable digital workspaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time performance will contribute to the goal for natural communication • Streaming animated avatar data is only a fraction of video streaming cost • Validate the CORTEX2 developments against a solid baseline 	
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI Capture multiple users in room scale contexts: 4 • KPI Capture users in real time: 25Hz 	
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. A report containing the outcomes of the tasks, along with a remote demonstrator of the real-time multi-user marker-less MoCap PoC.</p>	

3.1.4. FLYTEX - Enhancing Videoconferences with Real-Time IoT Data in agrifood sector

		https://itg.es/en/flythings-industria-4-0/
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SME funded in 2016 • Spin-off of ITG, officially recognized National Technology Centre • Main product: Industrial IoT platform • Modular, flexible and scalable <p>The application of new technologies allows Flythings® to observe, by integrating artificial vision systems; to converse through a chat based on generative artificial intelligence; to learn thanks to the analysis of the data incorporated; and to predict through its advanced algorithmic system.</p>		Spain
Project Acronym	FLYTEX	
Project Title	Enhancing Videoconferences with Real-Time IoT Data in agrifood sector	
Expected Result	Transform video meetings and immersive environments by providing access to IoT data in videoconferencing applications, validating this technology in the agricultural sector, but applicable to several domains.	
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridging the gap between sensor-gathered data and users, enabling real-time user interaction with CORTEX² a • Enhancing monitoring, analysis, of data-driven insights and decision-making in agri-food sector • Increase efficiency and sustainability of agri-food sector • Revitalize rural economies 	
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full implementation of IoT adaptors and incorporation of provided CORTEX² IoT endpoints • Initial experimentation with real IoT sensors in lab environment • Support of various IoT measurement types (e.g. humidity, air quality, temperature). 	
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. The architecture definition and adaptors development for the integration with the CORTEX ² platform.	

3.1.5. MGL - Magos Gestures Library

	https://www.themagos.com/
<p>Quanta & Qualia (Q&Q) is a dynamic Greek startup specialized in systems engineering (H/W and S/W development, product design) in advanced electronics, mechatronics and embedded software and also innovation and technology management skills. Core business is the development of innovative technological products in the Human Computer interaction sector. MaGOS, its flagship product is a wearable solution-patent applied-which re-invents the finger/hand tracking methodology in 3D environment.</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>MGL</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Magus Gesture Library</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Integrate Magos gloves and develop the Magos Gestures Library (MGL) module into the CORTEX² framework, enhancing the landscape of XR applications. The project will produce a UnityPackage for seamless adoption and implementation.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Next-generation Gesture Solution: revolutionize gesture recognition, leveraging the best in market accuracy of Magos gloves in the AR/VR domain, opening new markets and opportunities. • Enhanced XR Experience: MGL module will enhance XR applications, including simulations, collaboration, training, and gaming. By integrating MGL, users will experience advanced capabilities in hand tracking and gesture recognition, elevating their overall XR experience.
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video showcasing demo • Technical specifications
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Module analysis and integration plan.</p>

3.1.6. MHI - Multiplayer Haptic Interactions

	SENSEGLOVE	https://www.senseglove.com/	Netherlands
<p>SenseGlove is an innovation driven company on a mission to create the mouse and keyboard of the future. We believe that in the era of the Metaverse digital interactions will feel as natural as the real ones: in addition to clicking and scrolling you will be able to touch, grab, hold and feel the virtual as if it was real. Already available for professionals using SenseGlove in their VR training solutions, these interactions will be ultimately a norm for everyone. Just like the mouse and keyboard today.</p>			
Project Acronym	MHI		
Project Title	Multiplayer Haptic interactions		
Expected Result	<p>Interact naturally with a minimum of 4 players in a VR training environment with some players wearing haptic gloves (SenseGlove Nova 2) and others using HMD hand tracking (Ultraleap or Meta) via the Cortex² framework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pass objects to players • Feel size and density of objects • Feel basic textures (e.g. water dripping) • User to user interactions like a handshake 		
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make easy multiplayer interactions with hand tracking and Haptic Gloves via SG interactions in Unity • Fast developments with a large library of pre-fab objects and interactions • Using hand tracking to interact with haptic glove users for budget reasons 		
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototype hand tracking system • Design multiplayer interaction rules • Integrated hand tracking into the SG interaction builder in Unit 		
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Module analysis: object interaction on single mode. Hand VR interaction		

3.1.7. RAX - Realistic Avatars for XR

	https://www.igoodi.eu/en/home
<p>Italian Avatar Factory with strong expertise in digitalization of the human body as a scalable solution for the masses along with precise anthropometric data (Smart Body), which enable a series of utility Use Cases in the areas of healthcare, wellness, fashion, gaming and more. IGOODI possesses patented technology of body scanning and production pipeline.</p>	<p>Italy</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>RAX</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Realistic Avatars for XR</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Project will develop unique, scalable, easy to use application where the user can create their own realistic, interoperable (2D/3D), compatible with major engines, customizable, purposeful Avatar</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>IGOODI will amplify its commercial proposition with a powerful tool, applicable and commercially exploitable in various vertical domains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial domains, telepresence, teleconferencing • Beauty & Fashion, products preview • Healthcare, results preview <p>Inclusivity: Avatar configurator based on realistic representation of a real person.</p>
<p>First achievements</p>	<p>The MVP application with all basic features and a set of content for basic configurations as proof of concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MVP app with integrated Avatar production capability <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avatar Production time: Creation of a customized avatar in 2D and 3D in less than 10 minutes • Configuration parameters: Possibility of editing at least 5 attributes of the avatar (e.g. hair color, hair style, clothes, accessories) • Ability to make avatars have a realistic appearance similar to that of the user.
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. MVP Development</p>

3.1.8. SENSO3D - Revolutionizing Virtual Spaces: SENSO3D's Comprehensive 3D Object Library

	https://sensomatt.pt/	
<p>SENSOMATT AI Solutions harnesses advanced artificial intelligence to provide intuitive, scalable, and efficient automation solutions for enhancing operational productivity and decision-making processes across various industries. They offer a comprehensive suite of professional AI services, delivering bespoke solutions in machine learning, natural language processing, and advanced human-machine interaction, tailored to meet the unique needs of any business.</p>		<p>Portugal</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>SENSO3D</p>	
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Revolutionizing Virtual Spaces: SENSO3D's Comprehensive 3D Object Library</p>	
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three learning environments: a traditional classroom, group study room, and individual learning space. • Mix of static and dynamic assets allowing users to modify environments. <p>Entertainment and Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two environments: one for entertainment (e.g., virtual concerts) and the other for cultural experiences (e.g., museums). • Mix of static and dynamic assets allowing users to modify environments. 	
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Realism in virtual environments due to high-quality 3D models. • Enhanced user experience with more interactive and immersive VR/AR content. 	
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and identification of suitable 3D object datasets • Basic design specs for each 3D object; Complete documentation • Aggregation and preprocess 3D object models and associated image data 	
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Design specification document.</p>	

3.1.9. TIP - The Infinity Palette

	https://www.3dinteractive.se/sv/index.html	
<p>3D Interactive Sthlm is a full service XR-development company with a full focus in creating, developing and distribution of immersive experiences and solutions within the area of Augmented, - Mixed- & Virtual Reality and have been doing so since 2012. Over the years they have acquired vast experience and developed a deep know-how in working with and developing applications & services with 3D content as a core ingredient.</p>	<p>Sweden</p>	
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>TIP</p>	
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>The Infinity Palette</p>	
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three learning environments: a traditional classroom, group study room, and individual learning space. • Mix of static and dynamic assets allowing users to modify environments. <p>Entertainment and Culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two environments: one for entertainment (e.g., virtual concerts) and the other for cultural experiences (e.g., museums). • Mix of static and dynamic assets allowing users to modify environments. 	
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance learning with visual environments. • More accessible education. • Quicker onboarding through example environments. • Higher student retention. • Encourages user creativity 	
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refine project specification. • Planning & conceptualizing of environments. • Inventory of 3D Interactive's existing asset library. • Validation of inventory. 	
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Design specification document.</p>	

3.1.10. VISOR - Virtualization Service for Object Reconstruction

 PHASMATIC	https://www.phasmatic.com/
<p>Phasmatic™ was founded in 2022 and is a 3D graphics-focused company located in Corfu & Athens, Greece. The team members have previously worked in academia, research centers, serious & VR games, and semiconductor industries. Their mission is to develop world-leading software solutions to enrich visual user experiences with cutting-edge 3D photorealistic rendering technology.</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>VISOR</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Virtualization Service for Object Reconstruction</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalize objects to share virtually with distant partners • Usage of a simple camera or smartphone to digitalize small objects • Digital-twin-as-a-service • Live 3D object reconstruction
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated, flexible, high quality 3D objects • Instant 3D object reconstruction • Compatibility with any pipeline • Multiple stakeholder collaboration • Ever-expanding 3D asset library • Facilitate broad adoption for the next-generation of XR technologies
<p>First achievements</p>	<p>Developed VISOR system's core components, including the front-end and back-end infrastructure, and began integration with the CORTEX² framework.</p> <p>The 3D reconstruction pipeline for converting 2D images or videos into 3D models has been validated through initial tests.</p> <p>KPI: successful object reconstruction.</p>
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Module analysis and integration plan. D4. Report on module technical development.</p>

3.2. OC1 use-cases

3.2.1. AgiVision - Extended reality for Efficient and Sustainable Farming

 https://www.uom.gr/en		
<p>bSpoke Solutions provides a wide range of services allowing a perfect alignment between strategic business objectives and digital transformation, covering new and improved ICT systems and operations, ubiquitous operating models, automation and AI adoption. Their digital transformation solutions include EcoTrace (empowering sustainable food choices), XR-Shield (Advanced XR technology for ship inspections).</p> <p>University of Macedonia - a public research university in Thessaloniki, Macedonia, Greece. Founded as School of Higher Industrial Studies of Thessaloniki. It specializes in economic and social sciences.</p>		<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>AgriVision</p>	
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Extended reality for Efficient and Sustainable Farming</p>	
<p>Expected Result</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of XR with Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) - allowing farmers to visualize complex agricultural data intuitively: • Real-time Data Visualization and Decision Support that significantly reduces the time required for decision-making • Remote and Immersive Collaboration - leveraging XR to enable real-time, immersive interactions between farmers and consultants. 	
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Productivity & Efficiency: increase decision-making speed by 40% with real-time data visualization • Agricultural consultancy: real-time data and immersive consultation capabilities, enhancing service value. • Environmental: reduces resource waste by 20%, lowering the carbon footprint. • Economic gain: boosts farm profitability by up to 25% through improved yields and market adaptability • Knowledge Gap: Utilize XR'S immersive technology to make complex concepts accessible to new young farmers, speeding up the learning process 	

First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis – identification of key sectors needs and validation participants, integrating their feedback into planning. • Developed Initiate technical requirements and roadmap integrating AgriVision with CORTEX²
Submitted deliverable(s)	<p>D1. Specification and Implementation Plan.</p> <p>D2. Performance Report.</p>

3.2.2. C.A.R.E. XR - Critical Awareness and Response Enhancement with eXtended Reality

	<p>https://www.seeu.edu.mk/</p> <p>https://www.cuk.gov.mk</p>	
	<p>South East European University (SEEU) provides a set of unique study and research opportunities, shaped by a dynamic faculty. With more than 80 study programmes, we offer modern teaching methods, backed by certified quality management and advanced IT services. These opportunities are further enhanced by an active collaboration with the community and an integrated, ecologically sustainable campus.</p> <p>Crisis Management Center of North Macedonia (CMC) - an independent state administrative body, having the status and function of a directorate, which legal competences include gathering of information, assessment, situation analysis, objectives and tasks determination, development and implementation of the necessary actions for prevention, early warning and handling crises. The National Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction.</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>C.A.R.E. XR</p>	
<p>Project Title</p> <p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Critical Awareness and Response Enhancement with eXtended Reality</p> <p>Integration of XR with the Next-Generation Incident Command System (NICS) for enhanced situational awareness and decision-making in emergency management, fostering a more connected and informed response infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Develop and deploy an XR platform that integrates with NICS ○ Create an immersive XR System that will facilitate communication between first responders and planners ○ Implement ML and NLP that will summarize and prioritize messages passed during emergency situations 	

<p>Expected Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Situational Awareness during emergency situations • Improved Communication between first responders and planners • Redefining Emergency Management Standards • Boost in Research and Innovation • Enhanced Responder Safety and Efficiency • Socio-economic Impact – reduce human resources during emergencies • Commercial Potential and Intellectual Property • SEEU will solidify its status as a pioneer in XR technology, expanding its academic and research horizons. • CMC will experience a transformative enhancement in operational capabilities
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement Analysis and Specification • Technology Feasibility Study • Project Plan Development <p>The team demonstrated a solid understanding of the C.A.R.E. XR objectives by clarifying the functional requirements, the technologies to be adopted, and identifying potential integration risks of the NICS data collection platform with the CORTEX² framework.</p>
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.</p>

3.2.3. CORE-MHC - CO-facilitated and REMote Mixed-Reality Mental Health Care interventions

<p>https://fundacionsasm.org/</p>		
<p>INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE INFORMÁTICA (ITI) is a private Technology Centre dedicated to Research, Development and Innovation in Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), belonging to the Network of Technological Institutes of the Valencian Community (REDIT) and the Spanish Federation of Technological Centers (FEDIT). Since 1994, ITI has been developing R&D applied to the needs and problems of companies, seeking technological solutions that respond to social and economic challenges, improve industrial competitiveness, and promote a more intelligent and sustainable society.</p> <p>Fundación SASM was established in April 2001 as a social assistance organization, with the aim of providing social and health care, recovery and residence for people with chronic mental illness. For this reason, over time, the SASM Foundation has fought to obtain different resources for the care of</p>		<p>Spain</p>

	people with mental illness, with the aim of facilitating their inclusion in their social environment, promoting autonomy and improving their quality of life.
Project Acronym	CORE-MHC
Project Title	CO-facilitated and REmote Mixed-Reality Mental Health Care interventions
Expected Result	<p>Improve mental healthcare standards and ensure equal access to quality treatment, regardless of location or facility availability, leveraging Mixed Reality (MR) technologies to develop an engaging and accessible solution for remote therapeutic activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a 1 on 1 remote Mental Health Care (MHC) environment based on Mixed Reality (MR) built on the CORTEX2 platform. • Integrating rich contextual, real-time Internet of People (IoP) data generated by physiological sensors. • Co-design and implementation of collaborative, Mixed-Reality serious-games mechanics to improve intrinsic motivation, adherence, and effectiveness of treatments.
Expected Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address treatment gap and treatment drop-out: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Democratize access to mental healthcare ○ Increase patients' motivation and adherence to treatments ○ Demonstrate feasibility of MR-based mental health therapy ○ Novel and motivating therapeutic activities for patients ○ Support to monitoring patients' evolution • Export MR collaborative platform to other domains (industry, education, etc.) • Advance state of the art of MR technologies and UX in MR settings • Validation of CORTEX² components on Mixed Reality headsets • Validation of CORTEX² components in mental health use-case scenario
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and evaluation of POC • Use Case Scenarios definition and KPIs • Roadmap for CORTEX2 framework integration and benchmarking of Technologies for XR in Health
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.

3.2.4. FocusVR-ADHD - ADHD VR Solutions

<p>www.rtelab.com</p>	<p>https://en.umed.pl/</p>
<p>RTE Lab sp. z.o.o. provides Mixed Reality solutions, developing advanced applications tailored for healthcare, education, and business training. It integrates AR/VR into patient treatment and rehabilitation, enhancing therapeutic outcomes with immersive technology. The company was chosen by EIT Health for a major healthcare initiative using GenAI to overcome market barriers and improve services through XR technologies,</p> <p>Medical University of Lodz (MUL) specializes in areas like psychodermatology and neuropsychiatric rehabilitation. MUL operates multiple clinics and research centers, producing over 300 publications that highlight its clinical impact. A leader in ADHD management, MUL pioneers innovative psychological treatments and extensive ADHD research.</p>	<p>Poland</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>FocusVR-ADHD</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>ADHD VR Solutions</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop immersive VR scenarios that improve cognitive functions in individuals with ADHD, utilizing the CORTEX² platform. • Enhance traditional ADHD treatment methods by engaging in VR technology to improve treatment outcomes
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased Engagement: FocusVR boosts engagement by immersing patients in interactive and captivating therapy scenarios tailored for ADHD. • Enhanced Effectiveness: Personalized VR scenarios specifically target ADHD symptoms like attention deficits and impulsivity, leading to improved treatment outcomes. • Personalized Treatment Process: Real-time analytics adjust therapies based on individual responses, ensuring each session is optimally effective for the patient. • Accessibility and Convenience: VR enables flexible therapy sessions at home, reducing the need for frequent clinical visits and enhancing therapy adherence.
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The UX journey has been specified (user story mapping) • Developed 1st demo as a Proof of Principle • KPI: successful deployment of the use case in the selected domain • KPI: N of different scenarios supported for the specific domain

Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.
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3.2.5. HYMNE - Hybrid Music, New Experiences

 https://4drstudios.com/	https://www.effenaar.nl/
<p>4DR Studios BV is the first and only volumetric video studio in the Netherlands and one of the few high-quality volumetric video studios in the world. They have both the people and the resources to execute high-quality volumetric video productions to perfection, capturing every detail of human movements and emotions.</p> <p>Effenaar Pop Venue has been a household name in Eindhoven for over fifty years. The iconic building, designed by Rotterdam architectural firm MVRDV, contains a multifunctional pop venue with two halls, a restaurant-café and its own backyard.</p>	
Project Acronym	HYMNE
Project Title	Hybrid Music, New Experiences
Expected Result	<p>Create the audience-centered HYMNE platform, democratizing immersive music experiences while creating a fair business model for the entire chain of creators and distributors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 different performances with volumetric video and spatial audio and interactive audience engagement, 1 experience using AR in a pop venue and 2 levels of interactive experiences in VR, that will showcase the hybrid music experiences in the operational HYMNE CORTEX platform
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a new innovative approach to reaching out with music to large live audiences. • a deeper understanding of the interactive needs of music fans. • substantially reduce production time and costs and we will reduce the risk and complexity of creating Hybrid music experiences. • create a fair and sustainable business model for the XR music industry
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The artistic and technical components have been specified to kick off development. • Strong highlights: utilization of multiple XR affordances; detailed plan of the components.

Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.
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3.2.6. SCIPLANT - Sustainable City Planning Tool

		https://www.thecarbongames.com/
<p>MERCURY RETROGRADE LDA</p> <p>The Carbon Games functions similarly to a venture studio but with a specific focus on sustainable digital mobility solutions. It develops, and launches various initiatives aimed at tackling environmental challenges through innovation in transportation and urban living.</p>		Portugal
Project Acronym	SCIPLANT	
Project Title	Sustainable City Planning Tool	
Expected Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower citizen participation in planning the future of their community • XR tech based on CORTEX² and leveraging its full capabilities for the shared user experiences of residents, cities, planners and more. 	
Expected Impact	<p>For City/Municipality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased transparency • citizen satisfaction • urban revitalization • data-driven decisions <p>For Planners/Third Parties</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaboration opportunities • new business • showcase expertise • innovation leadership 	
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement Gathering • UX Design & Integration Planning 	
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.	

3.2.7. SELFLEX2 - Real-Time remote dexterity training for “hands-on” industrial applications

<p>https://smartflexcell.com/</p>	
<p>CTAG - Automotive Technology Center of Galicia is a private and independent technology center whose strategy is oriented towards scientific and technical excellence, technological specialization and internationalization in the automotive, transport and mobility industry.</p> <p>SmartFlexCell Solutions S.A. - Flexible & Quickly Adjustable Robotic Cell Unique hexapod and software technology allowing to set up the robotic cell within minutes and switch from one order to the next. The hexapods act as an ever adjustable or holding fixture system. The robot cell adjusts itself based on your production drawings. With the help of the software, it's easily converted into the positioning of the fixture – no robot programming skills are required.</p>	<p>Spain</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>SELFEX2</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Real-Time remote dexterity training for “hands-on” industrial applications</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Introduce the real-time nature in this human-in-the-loop flow, thus allowing a real-time training between one teacher-senior operator in one location and several junior operators in remote locations, that can learn to execute dexterity-based tasks in real-time, by combining video, voice, and the Augmented-Reality representation of the hands of the teacher</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A reduction in the number of travels per employee will have a significant economic impact to the companies. • Retention of know-how and reduced downtime sometimes required until the training of new employees is completed.
<p>First achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target architecture clearly defined. • The use-case with end-user is well defined.
<p>Submitted deliverable(s)</p>	<p>D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.</p>

3.2.8. vScientist - Immersive Exploration of Fluid Dynamics: Developing an XR/VR Platform for CFD virtual testing in Education and Social Inclusion

<p>https://multifluidx.com/</p>	
<p>National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Technological adopter-leader School of Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering. State-of-the-art numerical simulations using CFD in HPC environments, large datasets for aerodynamics & hydrodynamics (in-house code MaPFlow). MultiFluidX - Lyras EE (R&D SME) with 30+ years combined experience in Machine learning & CFD simulation of industrial flows and cloud computing. Teaching experience. Proven VR/XR in-class experience. MPflow®: the first commercial ML-CFD code</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Project Acronym</p>	<p>vScientist</p>
<p>Project Title</p>	<p>Immersive Exploration of Fluid Dynamics: Developing an XR/VR Platform for CFD virtual testing in Education and Social Inclusion</p>
<p>Expected Result</p>	<p>Objective 1 (student-oriented): Develop a straightforward workflow for viewing CFD results and associated data in an immersive virtual environment (IVE)</p> <p>Objective 2 (lecturer-oriented): Develop multiple scenarios and visualise them within IVE</p> <p>Objective 3 (technology-oriented): Integrate an ML-CFD software (developed by MFX) within Cortex2 to instantly analyse 3D problems</p> <p>Increase student engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of complex geometries (ship propellers, wind turbine rotors etc) • Allow non-expert users to use fluid dynamics simulations to analyse problems • Provide CFD simulation results fast using ML techniques
<p>Impact</p>	<p>Introducing VR into research & collaborations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project will make CFD more accessible to a diverse group of learners • Reduce the entry barrier to cognitively complex learning subjects.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positively trigger cognitive skills & behavioral aspects of learning motivating students. • Improve learning outcome
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful deployment of the use case • Established a workflow for loading & viewing CFD datasets in Unity & Cortex²
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.

3.2.9. XRehab - Extended Reality for Neurological Rehabilitation

 https://www.deepreality.it/		
<p>NEMO LAB SRL - Center for Scientific Research and Technological Innovation in Neurological Field. The first Italian technological hub for the development of technological innovation projects in neurological diseases, called NLAB Research Center. They want to improve the quality of life of neurological community through the use of technological solutions.</p> <p>DEEP REALITY SRL is a young innovative company that aims to simplify the creation and use of VR and AR content. Thanks to their web apps, any user can easily create their own VR content, based on 360 panoramic photos, or their own AR content, with information displayed on real images.</p>		Italy
Project Acronym	XRehab	
Project Title	Extended Reality for Neurological Rehabilitation	
Expected Result	<p>Revolutionize rehabilitation through innovative VR technology. By designing a versatile VR simulation environment tailored for hospital settings, the project aims to enhance patient engagement, offer personalized rehabilitation experiences, and facilitate remote accessibility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve pain threshold • To stimulate learning • To Set up of the avatar of the patient 	
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Accessibility – Easier access to rehabilitation for better quality of life. 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote Monitoring – Efficient patient surveillance without needing constant physical presence. • Personalized Treatment – Tailored rehabilitation plans for individual needs. • Standard of Care – XRRehab becomes an integrated part of managing these diseases. • Positive Patient Outcomes– Advanced rehab and personalized treatment lead to better results.
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI achieved: Successful deployment of the use case in the selected domain – target value 4 • KPI achieved: Scenarios supported in the specific domain of Cortex platform – target value 4
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.

3.2.10. XRisis portfolio - Emergency Crisis Simulation & Preparedness Metaverse Toolkit

 https://www.actioncontrelafaim.org/		
<p>Nuwa Ltd - The team brings together a wealth of experience and expertise gained from 5 years of successful collaborations in the exciting realms of 3D, VR, and AR technologies across Ireland. With a deep understanding of these cutting-edge technologies, we have honed our skills to deliver innovative solutions that push the boundaries of what is possible.</p> <p>Action Contre La Faim Action Against Hunger is an international humanitarian NGO that has been fighting against world hunger for over 40 years.</p>		<p>Ireland France</p>
Project Acronym	XRisis	
Project Title	Emergency Crisis Simulation & Preparedness Metaverse Toolkit	
Expected Result	Collaborative Crisis Management, Preparedness & Simulation Trainings in the Metaverse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design a VR simulation environment 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Develop and implement an MVP• Validate the MVP - 3 pilot cases led by ACF• Promote XRisis Worldwide
Impact	Enhancement: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Experiential Learning• Wider Range of Training Scenarios• Critical Skills Acquisition• Emergency Response Preparedness Reduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• SOP Acquisition Time• Personal and Reputational Risks• Logistics and Training Costs
First achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Outlining the processes for the three pilots• Identifying and testing some components of CORTEX² framework• Comprehending the technological environment and its challenges to achieve integration.
Submitted deliverable(s)	D1. Specification and Implementation Plan. D2. Performance Report.

4. Monitoring, Mentoring, Evaluation

4.1. Monitoring

One of the forms of regular engagement with the selected parties is the ongoing monitoring process. It includes administrative communication, management of the Open Call programme execution and collection of feedback regarding the collaboration between the project and the 3rd parties.

4.1.1. Timeline of the Programme

Track 1 for co-developers follows 9-month and track 2 for use-cases 12-month (Figure 3). Both periods are directly supported by the Open Call CORTEX² Assistance Programme covering monitoring, mentoring and evaluation activities. Specifications of each of the tasks will be unfolded in further sections.

Figure 3 Timeline OC1 Programme for the 3rd Parties

4.1.2. Fundamentals of the Programme

The management of the Open Call programme is established in the CORTEX² project repository. This allows transparent monitoring, while controlling shared access to the key documents. Each of the Beneficiary has access to a **personalized file** with restricted entree (contracts; deliverables; review reports), and an **open access file** for all funded projects with supportive materials for the programme (branding guidelines, kick off meeting materials on the programme execution, templates).

The **programme fundamentals** are built around three pillars (Figure 4):

- Technology development, deployment, integration and validation.
- Collaboration and communication between different parties.

- Exploitation of the funded results.

Figure 4 Open Call programme management - three main pillars of focus

4.1.3. Feedback about the Programme

F6S performs bi-monthly surveys targeting two groups: 1) Funded projects; and 2) Mentors. The objective of this task is to collect regular transparent feedback on 20 ongoing collaborations happening in the Open Call CORTEX² programme.

- **Survey for Sub-granted projects monitors:**
 - Beneficiary progress overview between Sprints/Phases
 - Any challenges faced
 - Feedback about collaboration with Mentor
 - How the Beneficiary would like to expand the collaboration with CORTEX²
 - Any need for training, workshops, etc.
 - Level of satisfaction from Beneficiaries about the programme, activities, and support provision.
- **Survey for Mentors monitors:**
 - Relevant feedback on collaboration
 - Spotting any challenges ahead of time, if relevant
 - Sharing ideas for training/workshops suggested by Mentors
 - What support Mentor may need from the CORTEX² consortium

F6S collects feedback, analyses it and acts on addressing it. Administrative matters are dealt with by F6S, while feedback regarding technology progress, and mentors are communicated directly to DFKI that leads the mentoring activities.

The expected outcome from the regular monitoring activities is to secure the best possible conditions for fruitful collaborations. Active listening to the needs of all involved parties, clear communication, keeping everyone engaged and accountable play an essential role for the final innovative work results and successful funding management.

Figure 5 Roadmap for successful collaboration in OC1 Programme

4.1.4. Additional support – tailored workshops

CORTEX² has planned to organize several internal workshops for the Third parties, covering deeper understanding of the project technology, and ethical and psychosocial factors aligned with the CORETX² objectives.

One of the first activities planned is also a matchmaking online event for all 30 funded projects. It will be an occasion to build synergies and enhance testing and validation collaboration between technology developers with technology adopters.

4.2. Mentoring

Within the duration of the Programme each Beneficiary is appointed by a Lead **Mentor**. The Mentor is an individual from the CORTEX² consortium with an expertise and interest most relevant in the topics and solutions being addressed within the sub-grant funded project. The Mentor's role is to observe, provide feedback, support and contribute to the evaluation of the Beneficiary's work progress.

The Mentor's work (Mentorship) is designed by F6S and led by DFKI (Figure 6). In OC1 there are 11 Mentors assigned from five organizations in CORTEX² Consortium (DFKI – 5; ACTIMAGE – 2; ICOM – 1; ALE – 2; LINAGORA – 1).

The essential part of Mentor's work is to assure access to CORTEX² Rainbow Multimodal Collaborative Platform during design, integration and validation of funded technologies and use cases. They remain a technical bridge between the 3rd parties and the rest of Consortium. The list of their tasks is included in Figure 7.

The list of assigned organizations representing each Mentor is presented in Table 1 and Table 2 for OC1 Track and OC1 Track 2 respectively.

Figure 6 OC Mentorship Programme structure

Figure 7 OC1 Collaboration with Mentors - responsibilities

Table 1: Mentors' assignment – OC1 Track 1 co-development

Mentors' assignment – OC1 Track 1 co-development					
#	Project	Title of the project	Lead Beneficiary	Country	CORTEX² Mentor Organization
1	ARY	ARY the AR Media	ARY	France	DFKI

D6.4 Third part achievements and impact version 1

2	CDLPG	Co-development of a Dynamic library of personalized gestures	Sensorama Lab	Ukraine	DFKI
3	EXTERNALISE	Enabling support for externalizing models in XR collaboration	MOVESE	Greece	ACTIMAGE
4	FLYTEX	Enhancing Videoconferences with Real-Time IoT Data in agrifood sector	FlyThings Technologies	Spain	ICOM
5	MGL	Magos Gestures Library	QUANTA & QUALIA	Greece	DFKI
6	MHI	Multiplayer Haptic interactions	SenseGlove	Netherlands	ACTIMAGE
7	RAX	Realistic Avatars for XR	IGOODI SRL	Italy	DFKI
8	SENSO3D	Revolutionizing Virtual Spaces: SENSO3D's Comprehensive 3D Object Library	Senso3D	Portugal	ALE
9	TIP	The Infinity Palette	3D Interactive Sthlm	Sweden	ALE
10	VISOR	Virtualization Service for Object Reconstruction	Phasmatic PC	Greece	DFKI

Table 2: Mentors' assignment – OC1 Track 2 use-cases

Mentors' assignment – OC1 Track 2 use-cases					
#	Project	Title of the project	Lead Beneficiary	Country	CORTEX ² Mentor Organization
1	AgriVision	Extended Reality for Efficient and Sustainable Farming	bSpoke Solutions L.P.	Greece	DFKI
2	C.A.R.E. XR	Critical Awareness and Response Enhancement with eXtended Reality	South East European University	North Macedonia	Linagora
3	CORE-MHC	CO-facilitated and REMote Mixed-Reality Mental Health Care interventions	INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE INFORMÁTICA	Spain	ALE
4	FocusVR-ADHD	FocusVR: ADHD VR Solutions	RTE Lab	Poland	ALE

D6.4 Third part achievements and impact version 1

5	HYMNE	Hybrid Music, New Experiences	4DR Studios BV	Netherlands	DFKI
6	SCIPLANT	Sustainable City Planning Tool	MERCURY RETROGRADE LDA	Portugal	ALE
7	SELFEX2	Real-Time remote dexterity training for “hands-on” industrial applications	CTAG	Spain	ALE
8	vScientist	Immersive Exploration of Fluid Dynamics: Developing an XR/VR Platform for CFD virtual testing in Education and Social Inclusion	NTUA	Greece	ACTIMAGE
9	XRehab	Extended Reality for Neurological Rehabilitation	NEMO LAB SRL	Italy	ACTIMAGE
10	XRisis	Emergency Crisis Simulation & Preparedness Metaverse Toolkit	Nuwa Ltd	Ireland	ACTIMAGE

4.3. Evaluation

The process of evaluation follows a cascade funding timeline with three check points presented in Figure 2 Open Call 1 roadmap of progress execution. Schedules of each of the Tracks are presented in Figure 8. During each Sprints/Phases the Beneficiaries are required to submit a set of materials demonstrating achieved progress. Once the required reports are delivered, third parties are invited to a brief review call.

Figure 8 OC1 programme: Timeline of evaluation check points Track 1 and Track 2

The details of each evaluation step are presented in the next sub-sections.

4.3.1. Step 1 Submission of deliverables and KPIs status

The Beneficiaries at the end of each Sprint/Phase submits deliverable(s) and provide status on the contracted KPIs (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

Insert Project ACRONYM & DX.X Full title

1. Introduction
1.1. Name what you need.

2. Objective
2.1. Name what you need.

Please describe the objective of this deliverable.

3. Developments & key achievements
Please describe the overall work performed and key achievements: visuals, tables highly appreciated: include screenshots, images, links if applicable

4. KPIs status
Please update the status of the contracted KPIs (focus on the relevant KPIs aligned with this deliverable. Regarding the rest of the KPIs you can write in the status when they are planned to be achieved.

KPIs list				
Number	Name	Measure and description	Benchmark	Status

Table 1: KPIs status

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Insert Project ACRONYM & DX.X Full title

5. Deviations
In case of any deviations please describe them and introduce mitigation measures.

6. Conclusion
ANNEX (use it when you need it)

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Figure 9 OC1 Track 1 - Deliverable template

Insert Project ACRONYM & DX.X Full title

1. Introduction
1.1. Add subsections as relevant.
Provide a short intro to the deliverable

2. Objective
2.1. Add subsections as relevant.
Please describe the objective of this deliverable.

3. Summary of progress
Provide a summary of the main progress made, key results achieved, and any issues faced. This section should provide foundations for the following sections.

4. Developments & results
Please describe the overall work performed and key results, achievements. Visuals, tables are highly appreciated: include screenshots, images, links if applicable

5. KPIs status
Please update the status of the contracted KPIs (focus on the relevant KPIs aligned with this deliverable. Regarding the rest of the KPIs you can write in the status when they are planned to be achieved.

KPIs list				
Number	Name	Measure and description	Benchmark	Status

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Insert Project ACRONYM & DX.X Full title

KPIs list				
Number	Name	Measure and description	Benchmark	Status

Table 1: KPIs status

6. Deviations
In case of any deviations please describe them and introduce mitigation measures.

7. Promotion activities
Describe here any activities carried out to promote the project. Consider the table below as a basis for reporting.

Promotion activity	Type of activity	Date of activity	Type of audience/ no. of people reached	Link/evidence

8. Planning for the next stage (if applicable)

9. Conclusion
ANNEX (use it when you need it)

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Figure 10 OC1 Track 2 - Deliverable template

D6.4 Third part achievements and impact version 1

Both Sprint 1 and Phase 1 required submission of the Implementation Plans (Figure 11 and Figure 12). The planning serves as a management tool for Beneficiaries and Mentors to keep track and manage all funded activities.

Figure 11 OC1 Track 1 - Implementation Plan & KPIs track template

Figure 12 OC1 Track 2 - Implementation Plan & KPIs track template

4.3.2. Step 2 Review call

In October 2024, OC1 programme performed 20 review calls with each funded project from both tracks. The goal of the review was to present a progress during an online call and give opportunity for discussion about activities performed, any challenges occurred and next steps.

An agenda included a pitch given by the lead Beneficiary, followed by Q&A session by reviewers.

Each call was organised and moderated by F6S. Mandatory participation was required for:

- DFKI coordination representative
- Lead Mentor
- Lead Beneficiary

This activity will continue at the end of the remaining Sprints/Phases for Track 1 and Track 2 respectively. The same review system will apply to OC2 programme.

4.3.3. Step 3 Review report

The final step in the review process requires construction of a Review Report that is delivered to the Beneficiary. It includes assessment of the progress from the assigned Mentor and review of the deliverables. The deliverables are always evaluated by two reviewers from CORTEX² – lead Mentor and other expert aligned with expertise needed.

Each Review Report indicates overall satisfaction level with the achievements with that varies between:

- **Excellent progress** (the project fully achieved its objectives)
- **Good progress** (the project achieved most of its objectives with minor deviations)
- **Acceptable progress** (Some objectives are achieved; corrective actions are required)
- **Unsatisfactory progress** (Urgent corrective actions or the project will be stopped)

99% of the funded projects were assessed as excellent and good progress.

The final Review Report is complemented by a set of recommendations, if relevant. ANNEX A: OC1 Review Report Track 1 and ANNEX B: OC1 Review Report Track 2 provide templates for Sprint 1 and Phase 1 respectively.

EVALUATION & REVIEWS

- **What form:** online video call
- **How long:** approx. 30-45 min
- **Who will evaluate?** Mentor, and 2nd reviewer
- **What will it cover?**
 - ✓ Ppt by the Beneficiary showing progress against contracted deliverables, KPIs per sprint/phase, dissemination activities, impact, any risks or deviations
 - ✓ Q&A
- **When?** Approx. one week after each sprint/ phase ends

Deliverables

✓ (Green checkmark icon) ✗ (Red minus icon)

5. Expected Impact

The selected third parties are key elements for CORTEX² Consortium to enlarge the ecosystem, the outreach, the technology, and the value proposition of the CORTEX² platform (Figure 13). The impact though goes far beyond CORTEX² needs (Table 3), having potential to influence a diverse list of identified target audience in D6.1 (Figure 14).

Figure 13 : Expected impact from the 3rd Parties projects

Figure 14 CORTEX² Target Audience

In Third party project portfolios section, each portfolio covers brief information about specific expected impact per project. Updates on the impact achieved will be regularly monitored and updated at the next deliverable.

Table 3: List of expected impact from 3rd parties' projects on different stakeholders

For CORTEX² technology and ecosystem

- Adds Value to the Cortex Marketplace
- User base growth
- Higher user engagement
- Broader acceptance of VR/AR technologies in industries
- Reinforce Cortex² position as an enabler of advanced technology solutions within the VR/AR Landscape
- The developments provided by Beneficiaries will make it possible to optimize and enhance the various use cases defined in the CORTEX2 Pilots
- Expanding testing environments of new sectors

For Beneficiaries

- Improve their core technology with multi-user and details capture of new XR features
- Development of a marketable product that enhances the team's expertise
- Insights after integration into a real-time communication platform
- Validation of technology in different use cases
- Exploitation of the results through new markets
- Exploration of new strategic partnerships and collaboration within the XR Ecosystem
- Potential to increase sales

For End users

- Advanced collaboration tool
- Improved realism in virtual environments
- Enhanced user experience with more interactive and Immersive VR/AR content
- Education sector:
 - Enhance learning experience especially in areas where detailed representations can aid in understanding complex concepts
 - More accessible education
 - Quicker onboarding through example environments
 - Higher student retention

- Encourages user creativity

For Market and Industry

- Support the technology transfer towards the 'Industrial Ecosystem', bridging the open innovation gap
- Introduction of innovative tools can stimulate market growth and competition
- Potential Reduction in development costs and time-to-market for VR/AR applications

For Society and Socioeconomic aspects

- Creation of new job opportunities in Tech developments
- Democratization of VR/AR development tools potentially leads to increased digital literacy.

At the completion of the funded projects, each Beneficiary will submit an Impact Assessment measuring the final effect.

4. Conclusion

Open Calls are strong mechanisms contributing to overall success of CORTEX². Funded third parties have a key role in validating, advancing and demonstrating the technical features offered by CORTEX². To this end, **CORTEX² had successfully performed two Open Calls, which developments and outcomes are expected to significantly expand the value of CORTEX².**

The current document summarizes the management structure designed for review, monitoring and mentoring support to the third parties. These assistive and control activities have led to positive collaborations reflected in first tangible results achieved, and clear plans for the next Sprints and Phases.

Given the multidisciplinary nature of the funded projects, CORTEX² is expecting to reach various impacts across well-targeted segments of the stakeholders. This ambition is aligned with the exploitation plans presented in D6.1 with key focus on industrial ecosystem, digital technology providers and social innovation sector.

Within the scope of the engagement activities, the Consortium is planning an online synergy event for all 30 funded projects. Specifically, it will facilitate connections between projects developing various modules and features and the use-case projects, fostering discussions about potential testing and integration opportunities within the ongoing Open Call 1 and 2 programmes. The goal is that the connections made during this event will lead to lasting collaborations that extend well beyond the programme itself.

The project will **continuously monitor and evaluate the funded project's outcomes**, while enhancing fruitful collaborations leading to greater impact beyond the closed borders of the project. The next deliverable 6.8 will report on the final achievements from both Open Calls programmes, covering the update on the human and ethical factors involved in the implementation and validation of new technology solutions.

6. ANNEX A: OC1 Review Report Track 1

CORTEX2 Open Call 1 Track 1 Review Report: Sprint 1

- | | |
|---------------------|--|
| Date of Review | Dd/mm/yyyy |
| OC1 Project Acronym | |
| Track | 1 co-development |
| Sprint 1 | Development |
| Sprint 1 goal | Fine tune planning & technology usage of CORTEX ² |
| Sprint 1 duration | 3 months |

Technical excellence of the project
Any remarks?

Technology usage/integration to CORTEX²
<i>Give a short evaluation of the technology development and the process of integration it to the CORTEX2 platform/ecosystem in this sprint. Any risks or failure occurred in this stage?</i>
Any remarks

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OC1 Track 1 Review Report – Sprint 1 DEVELOPMENT

Impact
<i>Give a short evaluation of the expected impact. Is it satisfactory? Do you have any objections?</i>
Any remarks

Collaboration between mentor and 3rd party
<i>Please express your experience of collaboration during this sprint. Are you satisfied with the level of collaboration and communication with the 3rd party? What have you appreciated the most. Do you have any recommendations?</i>

Overall Evaluation for this sprint – please choose one of the below

<input type="checkbox"/>	Excellent progress (the project fully achieved its objectives)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Good progress (the project achieved most of its objectives with minor deviations)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Acceptable progress (Some objectives are achieved; corrective actions are required)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unsatisfactory progress (Urgent corrective actions or the project will be stopped)

List of recommendations:

1. Please insert if applicable
2. ...

Sprint requirement:

Contracted outcome of the SPRINT 1	Status (achieved, partially, delayed)	Comments

2

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OC1 Track 1 Review Report – Sprint 1 DEVELOPMENT

Design and integration plan		
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List of deliverables

Deliverable title	Comments & recommendations if any	Accepted/Rejected

List of KPIs

The project has finalised the sprint. Please list and comment the main KPIs achieved by the time

#	KPI name	Target value	Status (achieved, pending, delayed, other)	Comment
1				
2				
3				
4				
...				

Mentor full name	
Organisation	

3

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7. ANNEX B: OC1 Review Report Track 2

CORTEX2 Open Call 1 – Track 2 Review Report: Phase 1

Date of Review	dd/mm/yyyy
OC1 Project Acronym	
Track	2 Use case
Phase 1 name	Requirements
Phase 1 goal	Set the implementation plan, including key requirements and roadmap for the use-case
Phase 1 duration	3 months

Technical excellence of the project

Give a short evaluation of the technological achievement. Is the work fully completed according to the plan? Can you list at least 3 strong points and any weak points if applicable.

Any remarks?

Technology usage and use case integration to CORTEX²

Give a short evaluation of the technology development and use case planning including a process for integration to the CORTEX2 platform/ecosystem. Any risks or weak points observed at this stage?

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OC1 Track 2 Review Report PHASE 1: REQUIREMENTS

Any remarks

Impact
 Give a short evaluation of the expected impact. Is it satisfactory? Do you have any objections?

Any remarks

Expected outcomes
 Were all expected outcomes as defined in Annex 1 Guidelines for applicants achieved during this phase, including:
 The delivery of two deliverables, namely:

- D1. Specification and Implementation plan (including UX, requirements and detailed roadmap for CORTEX2 framework integration, development and deployment of the use-case)
- D2. Performance Report (End of Phase 1)

The content of the deliverables should include:

- Description of how the project will be carried out.
- Description of the technologies to use.
- Reporting of the technical development.
- List of detailed milestones, deliverables and KPIs to achieve (metrics and target values for how the success will be determined).
- POC plan illustrating the use-case and the technology they will bring.
- User stories, if applicable.

Please, provide a short justification.

Collaboration between mentor and 3rd party

2

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OC1 Track 2 Review Report PHASE 1: REQUIREMENTS

Please express your experience of collaboration during this phase. Are you satisfied with the level of collaboration and communication with the 3rd party? What do you appreciate the most. Do you have any recommendations?

Overall Evaluation for this phase – please select one:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Excellent progress (the project fully achieved its objectives)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Good progress (the project achieved most of its objectives with minor deviations)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Acceptable progress (Some objectives are achieved; corrective actions are required)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unsatisfactory progress (Urgent corrective actions or the project will be stopped)

List of recommendations:

1. Please insert if applicable
2. ...

Phase requirement:

Contracted outcome of the PHASE 1	Status (achieved, partially, delayed)	Comments
Implementation plan, key requirements and roadmap for the use-case		

List of deliverables

Deliverable title	Comments & recommendations if any	Accepted/Rejected

List of KPIs

3

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OC1 Track 2 Review Report PHASE 1: REQUIREMENTS

The project has finalised the sprint. Please list and comment the main KPIs achieved by the time.

#	KPI name	Target value	Status (achieved, pending, delayed, other)	Comment
1				
2				
3				
4				
...				

Mentor full name	
Organisation	
Signature	

|

4

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